

PRECISION DIELECTRIC MEASUREMENTS USING A MODE-FILTERED
CYLINDRICAL CAVITY RESONATOR
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Abstract

A 60 mm diameter cylindrical cavity resonator used at NIST for high-accuracy ($|\Delta\epsilon'_d/\epsilon'_d| < 5 \times 10^{-4}$) permittivity measurements on low-loss materials is described. The cavity operates at X-band in the TE_{01p} mode and is of the mode-filtered type with helically wound walls. Measurement data on representative dielectric materials are presented together with an uncertainty analysis.

Introduction

In response to renewed interest in measuring the electromagnetic properties of materials, the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) has reestablished its materials measurements program. The major goals of this program are to evaluate the measurement techniques currently being used in industry, to provide standard reference materials that serve to validate their techniques, and to provide a measurement service for materials submitted by industry.

As part of this effort, a cavity resonator method was selected for early implementation because such measurement techniques are recognized as providing the greatest accuracy for relative complex permittivity ($\epsilon'_d - j\epsilon''_d$) measurements of low-loss, non-magnetic materials at microwave frequencies. The resonator is of the mode-filtered cylindrical type, operating in the TE_{01p} mode at X-band and is similar in design to units currently being used in the national standards laboratories of the United Kingdom and the Federal Republic of Germany [1,2]. The principal advantage of this form of cavity is that non- TE_{01p} modes are highly attenuated (>30 dB) because there is no axial current flow present.

Cavity Design

A cutaway view of the cavity resonator is illustrated in Fig. 1. The resonator consists of a 60mm diameter helically wound cylinder. The upper end plate is fixed and contains two narrow apertures through which the cavity is excited. The degree of coupling is loose ($S_{12} = -30$ dB at 10 GHz) giving an empty Q value of about 80,000 at 10 GHz. This value is approximately 75% of the theoretical Q value for a copper-walled cylindrical cavity. The placement of the slots is such that only the TE_{01p} mode and not the TE_{02p} mode, etc., is excited. The lower end-plate is movable, in order to allow for placement of the material sample in the cavity as well as to retune the cavity following sample insertion. The cavity length can be varied from 408.5 to 433.5 mm. The cavity body and tuner assembly are temperature controlled to within $\pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$ using circulating water. Further details are contained in [3].

Measurement Techniques

Some 17 TE_{01p} modes, where $p=15, \dots, 31$, are available for measurements in the 8.0 to 12.4 GHz frequency band coverage of the cavity. The actual mode selected depends upon the desired frequency of measurement and the need to avoid the presence of perturbing non- TE_{01p} modes. The measurement involves noting the change in modal parameters (resonant frequency and bandwidth) of the empty resonator versus that when a sample is present. In the fixed length method, the shift in the resonant frequency is noted, whereas in the fixed U.S. Government work not protected by U.S. copyright

Figure 1. Cutaway view of cylindrical cavity resonator.

frequency method the change in cavity length needed to compensate for the resonant frequency shift is noted instead. Permittivity (ϵ'_d) and loss tangent ($\tan \delta = \epsilon''_d/\epsilon'_d$) values are derived from the measured data, using existing theory [1,2,3].

Cavity Characterization and Uncertainty Estimates

Experiments are currently underway whose purpose is to fully characterize the empty resonator. Such characterization is important for correcting measurement data and determining systematic measurement uncertainties. Elements of this characterization process include determination of a) the impedance loading of the cavity created by the coupling apertures (see [3] for further discussion), b) the physical length and diameter of the cavity, and c) the ohmic losses of the cylindrical walls and end plates. These data are required for each of the 16 modes used for material measurements. In addition,

the perturbation effects created by the presence of the dielectric sample are being investigated. These can be significant when measuring high-permittivity materials. The effects include the presence of air gaps, changes in wall- and end plate losses and changes in aperture loading. Our current uncertainty estimates are $\pm 0.5\%$ in ϵ'_r and $\pm 10\%$ in $\tan \delta$. With anticipated improvements in cavity characterization and subsequent data corrections, the measurement accuracy can hopefully be improved by an order of magnitude.

Measurement Data

Fig. 2 shows ϵ'_r and $\tan \delta$ data obtained for a representative sample of fused silica glass. The data obtained using fixed length and fixed frequency methods appear to agree well. The increased spread in the data at the upper end of the frequency band (11 - 12.5 GHz) is due to the presence of perturbing TE_{02p} modes that begin to propagate at and above 11.2 GHz. The sample length is uniform to within $\pm 5\mu\text{m}$ and the sample faces are optically finished. The material is considered very pure and of very low loss. No corrections have been applied

to the measurement data. An error budget for the fixed-length measurement of this sample is given in [3].

REFERENCES

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Figure 2A. Relative permittivity (real part) data for fused silica sample.

Figure 2B. Loss tangent data for fused silica sample.